

Studies on the reaction of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate (16-DPA) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid

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Abstract : Reaction of 16-DPA (**1**) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (MCPBA) on activated silica gives selectively the 5,6-epoxy derivative **2** of **1** with an excellent yield of 91.75% whereas no selectivity was observed in solution phase reaction and a diepoxy (5,6 and 16,17) derivative **3** (as an isomeric mixture) is obtained.

Keywords : 16-DPA, 5,6-epoxy derivative, 5,6,16,17-diepoxy derivative, MCPBA, silica.

Introduction

Oxidation reactions of natural products are very important from synthetic as well as from biological point of view¹⁻³. Among all oxidation reactions, epoxidation is one of the most interesting field of research because of the proven biological activity of such type of compounds, viz. their mutagenic and cytotoxic behavior towards bacterial and mammalian cell⁴ and because of their application as a starting material towards valuable transformative reactions⁵⁻¹¹. MCPBA is known to be very useful for the oxidation and rearrangement of various types of natural and synthetic substances¹²⁻¹⁸. Although there are a few reports of reaction of steroidal skeletons with MCPBA^{19,20}, epoxide of 16-DPA as well as its derivatives are reported in literature. Previously, H₂O₂/HCOOH, MMPP or MCPBA in CHCl₃ at room temperature²¹⁻²³ etc. have been used for this epoxidation. However the selective epoxidation by MCPBA under solvent-free conditions has not been reported in literature. The presence of an unconjugated carbon-carbon double bond and an enone moiety in it prompted us to consider 16-DPA as a very interesting candidate to study its reaction with MCPBA. We report herein the epoxidation of 16-DPA with MCPBA in solution and in solid phase.

Results and discussion

The solid phase epoxidation reaction was carried out

at room temperature to yield the 5,6-epoxy derivative **2** whereas the same reaction afforded 5,6,16,17-diepoxy derivative **3** as an isomeric mixture in the chloroform under reflux. After usual workup, the residue in each case was chromatographed over a column of silica gel to furnish **2** and **3** (Scheme 1). These were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectroscopy.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on Shimadzu FT-IR 8300 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard, Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL-AccuTOF JMS-T100LC Mass spectrometer. Silica gel (60-120 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel-G (TB) for TLC.

Epoxidation of 1 with MCPBA on silica :

Solid support (silica gel 60-120 mesh, 1 g per 0.5 mmol of substrate **1**) was activated by heating (80 °C) in a laboratory oven for 2 h. The activated silica was then cooled to room temperature. 0.5 mmol of **1** and 1 mmol of MCPBA were then mixed intimately with activated silica in mortar and pestle. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred at room temperature for 1.5 h. Completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The

Scheme 1

reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl₃ (100 ml), washed with 10% NaHCO₃ solution (3 × 50 ml) followed by washing with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ (1 g) and chromatographed over a column of silica gel (8 g) to yield **2** exclusively in 91.75% yield in pet ether-ethyl acetate (94 : 6) eluent.

Epoxidation of **1** with MCPBA in chloroform :

0.5 mmol of **1** was dissolved in 15 ml of distilled chloroform. 1 mmol of MCPBA was added in small lots with continuous shaking. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 3 h. Completion of reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl₃ (100 ml), washed with 10% NaHCO₃ solution (3 × 50 ml) and washed with water. The combined chloroform extract was dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated and chromatographed over a column of silica gel (8 g) to yield **3** in 93.54% in pet ether-ethyl acetate (93 : 7) eluent.

Characterization data of epoxides **2** and **3** :

2 : White crystalline solid, m.p. 168.5 °C (Found : C, 74.16; H, 8.69; O, 17.18. Calcd. for C₂₃H₃₂O₄ (372.256) : C, 74.14; H, 8.66; O, 17.19%); IR (KBr) : 2943, 1733, 1701, 1660, 1585, 1245, 1039, 869 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) ppm : δ 0.87, 1.11, 2.01, 2.24 (4s, 4-CH₃), 2.89–2.92 (1H, m, H-6), 4.9–5.0 (1H, m, H-3), 6.67 (1H, s, H-16); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) ppm : δ 15.72, 20.35, 21.32, 21.45, 27.11, 27.22, 29.72, 32.01, 32.40, 35.24, 36.15, 36.65, 38.04, 46.10, 51.47, 56.28, 58.79 (C-6), 65.38 (C-5), 76.61, 143.99 (C-16),

155.25 (C-17), 170.19 (C-3 acetate carbonyl carbon), 196.69 (C-20 carbonyl carbon); MS : [M⁺] *m/z* 372, C₂₃H₃₂O₄, other characteristic peaks appeared at *m/z* 313, 270.

3 : White crystalline solid, m.p. 178.2 °C (Found : C, 71.10; H, 8.31; O, 20.62. Calcd. for C₂₃H₃₂O₅ (388.256) : C, 71.08; H, 8.30; O, 20.60%); IR (KBr) : 2925, 1726, 1701, 1560, 1245, 1035, 852 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) ppm : δ 4.9–5.0 (1H, m, H-3), 2.89–2.92 (1H, m, H-6), 3.66 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-16); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) ppm : δ 15.84, 20.05, 21.32, 21.18, 27.14, 27.32, 27.41, 27.52, 30.97, 31.36, 31.99, 32.09, 35.21, 36.02, 36.62, 37.95, 45.07, 45.57, 51.26, 58.72 (C-6), 60.45 and 60.22 (C-16), 62.64, 65.20 (C-5), 70.77, 71.24 and 71.18 (C-17), 170.54 and 170.22 (two isomeric C-3 acetate carbonyl peaks), 204.91 and 204.75 (two isomeric carbonyl group C-20); MS : [M+1]⁺, *m/z* 389 and [M+2]⁺, *m/z* 390. Other characteristic peaks appeared at *m/z* 371, 372, 346, 347. Assignment of all the carbons of **2** and **3** were made by comparison with ¹³C NMR spectral values accordance with literature²⁴.

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